

Practical application of textile permeability measurement

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Overview

- Background – permeability measurement
- Application of permeability measurement in industry
- Overview of the work at NPL
- Future work at NPL
- Update on second benchmark for compressibility and K_z permeability

Permeability measurement I

- Measurement of the resistance to flow of liquid through a material (i.e. a fibre preform)
- Important to characterise the permeability for liquid composite moulding (LCM) manufacturing techniques to support product quality control and simulation prediction to optimise resin flow through the product preform
- Three principal directions of measurement (K_1 , K_2 , K_3)
- Compression of preforms results in a significant decrease in permeability, therefore compressibility must also be measured

Permeability measurement II

- Technology is still at the research level and has not yet been fully translated into industry
- First radial, in-plane test standard has been produced. Other test methods have yet to be standardised.
- International benchmarking trials have been carried out for in-plane permeability, through-thickness permeability and compressibility
- Large standard deviations in the data remain for some measurements (>40% for through-thickness permeability measurements and >20% for compressibility).
- Benchmark trials focused on test **procedure**. How does this translate into application?

Permeability measurement in industry I

- Industry has recently started to use permeability measurement technology alongside flow simulation, with varied success
- Material manufacturers are not yet able to provide their own permeability data
- Industry requirements is for the manufacture of complex geometries to be simulated
- To be useful in simulating and enabling LCM techniques, permeability measurement procedures must work with the diverse resins and materials used by industry.
- Benchmark procedures use standard silicone oil instead of resin

Permeability measurement in industry II

- Extremely low permeability preforms are being introduced
- This works at the limits of equipment sensitivity and capability. A higher signal to noise ratio is seen
- The need for higher injection pressures contrasted against low permeability preforms exacerbates challenges of race tracking, i.e. the flow is forced around the edge of the preform
- Compressibility and tool deflection become more relevant factors
- Specimen preparation becomes more complex when validating and measuring the properties of such fabrics
- The presence of binders bring into question the temperature at which testing is carried out

The solution: design robustness into both equipment and procedures

Scaling up of measurements

- For industrial-scale testing, parameters such as speed and cost must be factored in, as measurements are directly related to productivity
- Hidden costs, such as the global shortage of silicone oil, begin to have an impact
- The tools used for data interpretation must be reconsidered – manual data interpretation becomes impractical and increases the risk of human error
- A complete digital industry solution to data capture and analysis would be extremely valuable

Improved specimen preparation

- Stack alignment and edge finish can be optimised by cutting specimen after stacking the individual layers
- The number of plies used must be minimised to keep material costs and specimen preparation times low

Research activities

- National measurement system (NMS) funded by the UK government to support Industry and academia
- Aims are to:
 - Support industry uptake of this technology through development of novel test rigs and procedures

Collaborate and support international research through benchmarking trials

Permeability measurement at NPL I

- Capability to measure in-plane, through-thickness and compressibility
- Equipment is compatible with resins (can be used at elevated temperatures)
- Optional cure monitoring capability

Permeability measurement at NPL II

- Co-organisers of international benchmarking trials for compressibility and through-thickness permeability
- Working with industry to deliver applied permeability measurement

Future work at NPL

- Development of increasingly robust test methods and equipment
- Working with industry to maintain the agility to meet industry needs
- Working in line with development towards standardisation, following the outcome of the NPL/NCC permeability measurement survey (2016)

Benchmark II - Kz and Compressibility

- Planned launch for early 2020. Completion within 18 months.
- Test procedure will be more specific, based on results of the first benchmarks
- Outputs: published papers and drafts for standardisation

Thank you

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